
A FRAMEWORK FOR OPTIMIZATION-AS-A-SERVICE IN MANUFACTURING

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents *optEngine*, a service-oriented shell for delivering Optimization-as-a-Service (OaaS) in modern manufacturing. Designed to address the limitations of tightly coupled, solver-specific optimization systems, *optEngine* introduces a novel middleware architecture that supports asynchronous and synchronous optimization workflows. The *optEngine* system offers a generalizable and cloud-ready optimization interface that aligns with Industry 4.0 principles, i.e., scalability, interoperability, and responsiveness. It is agnostic to optimization data schemas, allowing seamless integration with heterogeneous backend engines without requiring structural modifications. Its architecture combines a web-based API, durable message queues, and a schema-flexible data model to ensure scalability, robustness, and ease of deployment. A real-world case study from the automotive industry illustrates *optEngine*'s application in optimizing robotic operations within a kitting system, demonstrating both responsiveness and extensibility.

Keywords Optimization · OaaS · Manufacturing · Automotive Industry

1 Introduction

Contemporary manufacturing faces critical challenges, such as compliance with environmental regulations, resource constraints, inflationary cost pressures, supply-chain disruptions as well as geopolitical and trade uncertainty. Amidst such volatility, industrial organizations should be equipped with the tools required to meet these challenges. Such tools include the continuous optimization of manufacturing and logistics processes to maintain competitiveness Gröger

et al. [2012]. Thus, extensive research in recent years has been conducted to achieve optimal operating conditions in manufacturing systems and improve efficiency, productivity, and product quality Afteni and Frumuşanu [2017]. Such requirements stemming from manufacturing cases arising in the context of a Horizon Europe research project have motivated the development of optEngine, i.e., an optimization module acting as an interface shell—or layer—around the underlying optimization services needed in manufacturing.

The optEngine module is designed to support both asynchronous and synchronous (real-time) processing paradigms, enabling efficient and flexible data handling depending on the nature of the optimization task. One of its key features is its agnosticism to the specific data structures or formats required by different optimization algorithms or engines. Instead of enforcing a rigid data model, optEngine serves as a flexible intermediary; it receives data submitted by the end-user, stores it appropriately, and subsequently routes it to the relevant optimization service, as requested. This decoupling enables easier integration, high responsiveness, and scalability across various optimization workflows.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the broader context and motivations behind the need of optimization-as-a-service in manufacturing, highlighting related work. Section 3 presents the design and implementation of optEngine including its use cases, architecture, and technology stack. Section 4 describes a real-world industrial case study demonstrating how optEngine supports optimization in an automotive production environment. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper.

Table 1: optEngine Use Cases

Use Case	Description
UC1: Authenticate user	Authenticates the user by verifying credentials encoded in a base64 format included in each API request.
UC2: List optimization services	Returns the list of available optimization services (routes) to the authenticated user.
UC3: Submit asynchronous optimization job	Submits a new optimization job along with the required data and the service route identifier.
UC4: Get job status	Retrieves the current status and progress of a previously submitted optimization job using its UUID.
UC5: Cancel optimization job	Cancels an ongoing optimization job by referencing its UUID.
UC6: Get job solution	Fetches the solution data of a completed and successfully processed optimization job.
UC7: Store job solution	Stores the final solution of a completed job, submitted by the optimization service.
UC8: Submit synchronous optimization job	Submits a new optimization job, intended for real-time response, along with the required data and the service route identifier.

2 Background

Acknowledging the challenges that modern industry environments should address, decision support systems that rely on optimization are already employed, e.g., Plitsos et al. [2025], Koronakos et al. [2023], Plitsos et al. [2017], however the adoption of a more digitalized and service-driven discipline is imperative. To serve these needs, optimization technologies have increasingly shifted towards distributed, service-oriented architectures capable of delivering results on-demand and at scale.

A key trend in industrial decision support is the rise of Optimization-as-a-Service (OaaS), which delivers cloud-based functionalities—such as planning, batching, and ganging—without requiring local installation of optimization tools Giannetti [2011], Kurschl et al. [2014]. The NEOS Server concept is introduced in Fourer and Goux [2001] for framing ‘optimization as an Internet resource’ and demonstrating how solvers could be exposed through web interfaces to a global user base. Similar efforts have been made in the Optimization Services (OS) project, which proposed a distributed framework for implementing solvers, analyzers, and simulation engines as interoperable web services Fourer et al. [2010]. These works emphasize standardization and remote accessibility, laying the foundation for interoperable optimization components across the internet.

Several studies have traced the evolution of optimization tools from Application Service Provision (ASP) models to modular e-Services architectures. Works like that of Valente and Mitra [2007] have illustrated how distributed optimization components support embedded business analytics and decision engines in real-world operations .

Parallel to this, Cloud Manufacturing (CMfg) has emerged, integrating cloud computing, IoT, and service-oriented principles into cohesive platforms. In scheduling, for instance, cloud-based genetic algorithms have enabled collabora-

Figure 1: optEngine data Requirements

tive planning across distributed facilities in sheet metal production Helo et al. [2019]. This architecture highlights the importance of asynchronous, cloud-driven optimization engines in managing resource constraints and task sequencing. Beyond scheduling, CMfg platforms have also been extended to support large-scale personalized customization. Rewritable Petri Net (RPN) models combined with multi-objective optimization have been used for real-time reconfiguration in mass customization scenarios Wang et al. [2022]. This enhances both time and cost efficiency in real-world manufacturing scenarios by enabling systems to adjust autonomously to individual order requirements. Further studies on CMfg have classified service models (public, private, hybrid), outlined key enabling technologies, and discussed deployment challenges Tao et al. [2011]. Collectively, these works affirm the role of cloud-enabled, service-driven architectures in meeting the demands of flexible, adaptive manufacturing.

Additional platforms have explored the combination of simulation and optimization in distributed environments. A simulation-based optimization (SO) system was developed and tested in the aerospace sector, using web technologies (e.g., Ajax, ProtoBuf) to support industrial production optimization Syberfeldt et al. [2013]. Similarly, a web-enabled parallel SO platform was applied to automotive operations scheduling, showing how distributed computing mitigates the traditionally high run-time cost of simulation-based scheduling Andersson et al. [2007]. Service-based optimization has also been used in collaborative product design. One solution wrapped a process planning module—with methods like Tabu search—into a web-accessible service, interoperating with Extensible Markup Language (XML)-based feature representations to support remote process planning in distributed design teams Li [2005].

On the infrastructure side, real-time optimization is increasingly supported by reconfigurable manufacturing systems (RMS) and cyber-physical systems (CPS). Recent advances introduced software-defined environments (SDEs) that dynamically configure networks for time-sensitive communication flows, meeting the Quality of Service (QoS) needs of CPS-based production systems Nayak et al. [2015]. This work underscores the growing need for infrastructure-level flexibility to support both asynchronous and real-time optimization demands.

Building on the foundations established by OaaS, Optimization Services, and Cloud Manufacturing, optEngine introduces a novel middleware approach tailored to the demands of modern industrial optimization. Unlike previous systems that are often tightly coupled to specific solvers or data formats, optEngine is designed as a lightweight, cloud-ready, and schema-agnostic interface capable of supporting asynchronous optimization workflows. Its architecture enables seamless integration with digital twins, AI-based optimization models, and heterogeneous backend engines, making it suitable for complex decision-making tasks across industries such as automotive, steel, aluminum, and logistics. By decoupling data handling from algorithm execution and leveraging flexible web-based interfaces, optEngine democratizes access to advanced optimization capabilities, reduces system integration overhead, and aligns with the core tenets of Industry 4.0—scalability, interoperability, and responsiveness.

3 System Specifications & Design

The core functionality of optEngine is structured around a series of well-defined use cases that capture all essential interactions between the user, the system, and the optimization services. These use cases are summarized in Table 1.

optEngine is designed to support flexible, and both synchronous and asynchronous optimization workflows while remaining agnostic to the structure of the data exchanged with external optimization services. The entities involved in this process are the `User`, `OptimizationJob` and `OptimizationResult` classes, supported by an enumerated type defining job status values (i.e., `OptimizationJobStatus`).

Each authenticated User submits optimization requests through the HTTPS-secured Web API. When a request is received, the platform immediately creates an `OptimizationJob`—capturing the user, submission time, and JSON payload—and returns a unique job identifier, i.e., a UUID. Processing is fully asynchronous: clients poll dedicated endpoints to check the job’s `OptimizationJobStatus` (`PROCESSING`, `COMPLETE`, `FAILED`, or `KILLED`) and to download results once available. Internally, `optEngine` routes each job to the appropriate backend optimization service. In case an error occurs, the optimization service pushes the error to the status queue, while the end user is informed for this error via the `GET` (job status) call.

Upon successful completion of an optimization task, the system stores the result in an `OptimizationResult` instance. This result is linked to the original job via a shared UUID and includes the output data, again stored in a flexible JSON format to support heterogeneous optimization services. This model supports extensibility and robustness, ensuring that different optimization scenarios can be supported without changing the core platform. The structure of these classes and their relationships is illustrated in Fig. 1.

The development of `optEngine` leveraged a robust and modern technology stack to ensure scalability, reliability, and maintainability. The core of the application was built using Java 8 Corporation [2014] in combination with Spring Boot 2.4.5 Pivotal Software [2021], providing a lightweight and modular framework for building web services. The REST API was documented and exposed using Springdoc OpenAPI 1.5.2 Team [2021a], while Hibernate 1.0.0 Team [2001] facilitated seamless interaction with the underlying PostgreSQL 11 Group [2018] database. To enable asynchronous communication between services, RabbitMQ 3.8.16 Team [2021b] was employed as a message broker. Finally, Docker 18.09.7 Docker [2019] was used to containerize the application, simplifying deployment and ensuring environment consistency.

As noted above, `optEngine` is designed as a middleware shell that interfaces between users and multiple optimization services. Its architecture accommodates both asynchronous and real-time execution modes, and is agnostic to specific optimization data schemas. This design enables `optEngine` to flexibly support various optimization engines without requiring structural changes for each integration.

The internal data management of `optEngine` is structured around two primary forms of storage:

- Temporal storage is managed through durable message queues. These queues temporarily hold job-related data and control messages during the life-cycle of an optimization request. They play a crucial role in decoupling the interaction between `optEngine` and backend services, thereby enabling asynchronous communication and load balancing.
- Permanent storage is handled by a database, which is responsible for retaining job definitions, user data, job metadata (such as status and progress), and any relevant historical information. This ensures persistence and traceability of all optimization-related activities.

Figure 2: `optEngine` data Flow

To ensure generality and compatibility with different optimization services, all data exchanged within `optEngine`—whether stored in the database or transferred via queues—follows a flexible JSON-based schema. This schema-agnostic approach allows for easy adaptation to various data formats required by diverse optimization engines.

When a new optimization job is submitted, `optEngine` writes the job data to a designated queue associated with the requested optimization route. Each backend optimization service monitors its specific queue for incoming jobs. Upon receiving a job, the service processes the data and sends updates about the job’s status and progress to a status queue, while final results are written to result queues. Additionally, control queues support operations such as job cancellation.

Durable queue mechanisms provide fault-tolerance: even in cases of temporary service or infrastructure failure, job data remains available in the queue and can be reprocessed once services are restored. This design makes `optEngine` resilient and reliable under various operational conditions.

The full data and communication flow, including the API endpoints, queues, and service orchestration, is visually illustrated in Fig. 2. It captures the flow of data from the user’s initial request through to the backend processing and result retrieval stages.

4 Application of `optEngine` to the Automotive Industry

Optimization has already been employed to a wide range of challenges within the automotive industry, e.g., topology optimization of cast parts and engine calibration. However, as noted in Jones [2003], optimization is still employed far less frequently than anticipated, mainly because of obstacles such as incompatible design-and-engineering tools as well as difficulties in automating computer analyses, etc. In this regard, `optEngine` is developed to mitigate such problems.

To this end, we describe the application of `optEngine` on optimizing the operation of a Kitting Robotic System (KRS) that automates the pick-and-place process of the pre-assembly phase of vehicle production. In particular, the examined pick-and-place process Plitsos et al. [2025] involves a robotic arm that collects individual components from designated containers in a Gravity Rack (GR)—which serves as the storage area—and delivers them to specific positions in Kit Holders (KHs), e.g., Fig. 3. These KHs are then transferred to the assembly line as complete kits, ensuring that all required parts are available for downstream operations. The robot alternates between GR and KH nodes, following a strict sequence and adhering to precise movement durations measured in milliseconds Giannakos et al. [2025].

Figure 3: A Kitting Robotic System

To support different production needs, `optEngine` includes optimization calls that can adjust the robot’s actions or test alternative layouts. In this context, we identify three representative scenarios where optimization calls are triggered based on different production requirements. They reflect real-world requirements of automotive production, where rapid and accurate kit preparation is essential to maintain assembly line continuity and throughput. These cases involve both synchronous and asynchronous executions, depending on whether the optimization is required in real time or as part of a planning process:

- (i) Production Plan Optimization
- (ii) Automated Real-Time Pick-and-Place Execution
- (iii) Gravity Rack Layout Reconfiguration

The first case represents a typical production plan optimization call. In this case, `optEngine` receives a sequence of KH tuples (each tuple containing a specific number of KH) corresponding to the production plan for a given period of time, e.g., a whole week. Upon receiving the production plan, `optEngine` calls the appropriate algorithm (e.g.,

an exact method utilizing an Integer Programming model), which processes each KH tuple in the provided sequence to identify the most efficient pick-and-place path for each tuple, aiming to minimize total pick-and-place time. The analysis considers the current layout of the GR and the specific component requirements of each KH, ensuring that the robot operates efficiently. The output of the utilized algorithm is returned by `optEngine` and can be subsequently used by the manufacturer to program the corresponding KRS operations. A synchronous or asynchronous call to `optEngine` are utilized in this case, depending on the size of the underlying optimization problem and the computational needs of the optimization method utilized. For example, an asynchronous call can be used, if additional calculation time leads to improvement on the optimization objective (i.e., total pick-and-place time).

The second case corresponds to a real-time pick-and-place optimization call. In this case, a specific KH tuple and the current layout of the GR is provided to `optEngine`. Subsequently, `optEngine` invokes the appropriate algorithm (e.g., a fast heuristic such as the Nearest Neighbor) to identify the path that minimizes pick-and-place time for the whole KH tuple. The output of the utilized algorithm is returned by `optEngine` and then used by the manufacturer to update the corresponding KRS operations. The real-time nature of this case requires a synchronous call to `optEngine` coupled with a fast optimization algorithm (e.g., a heuristic). This enables the utilization of `optEngine` as a part of an implementation that enables automated KRS control. This leads to a 21% reduction in time for preparing the KHs, as measured and validated Plitsos et al. [2025]. For example, it can be used in a scenario (Figure 4) where a tuple of KHs arrives at the KRS via an Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV), the KRS identifies the required contents of the corresponding KHs, depending on their type, and triggers `optEngine` to obtain an efficient pick-and-place path for that KH tuple. Once receiving the optimization response, the KRS proceeds in filling in the KHs based on the provided response. Once the KHs are filled in, the AGV proceeds to the assembly area, while a new KH arrives at the KRS area and the process repeats. This can potentially fully optimize the whole KRS’s reprogramming time by 100% Plitsos et al. [2025].

Figure 4: Fully automated KRS optimization example

The third case shifts focus from production optimization to strategic layout optimization. The goal is to examine different configurations of the GR (i.e., different placement of component containers on the GR) in terms of reducing the total pick-and-place time for a given sequence of KH tuples (e.g., for a weekly production plan). In such a context, a specific sequence of KH tuples and a baseline GR configuration is provided to `optEngine` which in turn initiates a discrete event simulation method that examines multiple GR configurations against that KH sequence. For each configuration, `optEngine` calculates the total optimized pick-and-place time and identifies the layout that minimizes performance costs. This is particularly valuable when planning GR reconfigurations—such as after a component set change or layout redesign. Since the process explores several alternatives and does not require instant feedback, it runs independently and reports results once it is completed, thus requiring an asynchronous call. This leads to a 26% reduction in time for reconfiguring the KRS Plitsos et al. [2025].

5 Conclusion and future work

This paper presented the design, implementation, and real-world application of `optEngine`, a flexible optimization middleware shell, serving as interface between users and various optimization services in manufacturing. By supporting asynchronous execution modes, `optEngine` enables diverse optimization workflows tailored to the operational requirements of modern industrial environments.

The system’s architecture—characterized by its data schema agnosticism, modular design, and message-driven communication model—ensures extensibility, scalability, and fault tolerance across various use cases. Through its API-driven interface, `optEngine` serves as a powerful abstraction layer between users or systems and heterogeneous optimization services, promoting ease of integration and long-term maintainability. It is a significant step toward realizing service-oriented, cloud-compatible optimization in manufacturing, as it promotes interoperability, ease of deployment, and alignment with Industry 4.0 requirements.

The application of `optEngine` to the automotive sector demonstrates how it facilitates real-time decision-making as well as strategic planning through different optimization scenarios, including schedule validation, layout testing, and robotic sequencing. These examples highlight the practical benefits of optimization-as-a-service in complex, time-sensitive production environments.

A promising direction for future research is integrating ontology-driven mechanisms into optEngine to enable automatic classification of optimization problems based on input data. This could involve developing a domain-specific ontology that captures common problem types—such as scheduling, routing, and layout optimization—along with their typical data patterns. By semantically analyzing submitted JSON payloads, optEngine could infer the problem category and route it to the appropriate solver without manual input. Enhancing this with semantic annotations using standardized ontologies, i.e., AAS sub-model templates for manufacturing Gannouni et al. [2024], would allow the system to understand constraints, objectives, and entities in context, enabling dynamic solver selection and tuning. Additionally, it would link optEngine to Industry 4.0 ontologies and constructing a knowledge graph of problems, solvers, and outcomes, supporting historical reasoning. These enhancements would make optEngine more autonomous, scalable, and responsive to complex, data-driven manufacturing needs.

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References

- Christoph Gröger, Florian Niedermann, and Bernhard Mitschang. Data mining-driven manufacturing process optimization. In *Proceedings of the World Congress on Engineering*, volume 3, 2012.
- Cezarina Afteni and Gabriel Frumușanu. A review on optimization of manufacturing process performance. *International Journal of Modeling and Optimization*, 7(3):139–144, 2017.
- S. Plitsos et al. Enabling production re-configurability through digital twins: a case study approach. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, pages 1–24, 2025.
- G. Koronakos, Y. Smirlis, S. Plitsos, E. Tzannatos, A. Karalis, and K. Poutos. Optishop: A platform to support decisions during ship’s life cycle. In *Proc. 14th Int. Conf. Information, Intelligence, Systems & Applications (IISA)*, pages 1–6, Volos, Greece, July 2023. doi:10.1109/IISA59645.2023.10345960.
- S. Plitsos, P. P. Repoussis, I. Mourtos, and C. D. Tarantilis. Energy-aware decision support for production scheduling. *Decision Support Systems*, 93:88–97, Apr 2017. doi:10.1016/j.dss.2016.09.017.
- Fabio Giannetti. Oaas: Optimization as a service. In *NIP & Digital Fabrication Conference*, volume 27. Society of Imaging Science and Technology, 2011.
- Werner Kurschl et al. Concepts and requirements for a cloud-based optimization service. In *2014 Asia-Pacific Conference on Computer Aided System Engineering (APCASE)*. IEEE, 2014.
- R. Fourer and J.-P. Goux. Optimization as an internet resource. *Interfaces*, 31(2):130–150, 2001. doi:10.1287/inte.31.2.130.10629.
- Robert Fourer, Jun Ma, and Kipp Martin. Optimization services: A framework for distributed optimization. *Operations Research*, 58(6):1624–1636, 2010.
- Patrick Valente and Gautam Mitra. The evolution of web-based optimisation: From asp to e-services. *Decision Support Systems*, 43(4):1096–1116, 2007.
- Petri Helo, Duy Phuong, and Yuqiuge Hao. Cloud manufacturing–scheduling as a service for sheet metal manufacturing. *Computers & Operations Research*, 110:208–219, 2019.
- Min Wang et al. An optimal production scheme for reconfigurable cloud manufacturing service system. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, 18(12):9037–9046, 2022.
- Fei Tao et al. Cloud manufacturing: a computing and service-oriented manufacturing model. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part B: Journal of Engineering Manufacture*, 225(10):1969–1976, 2011.
- Anna Syberfeldt et al. A web-based platform for the simulation–optimization of industrial problems. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 64(4):987–998, 2013.
- Marcus Andersson et al. A web-based simulation optimization system for industrial scheduling. In *2007 Winter Simulation Conference*. IEEE, 2007.
- W. D. Li. A web-based service for distributed process planning optimization. *Computers in Industry*, 56(3):272–288, 2005.

- Naresh Ganesh Nayak, Frank Dürr, and Kurt Rothermel. Software-defined environment for reconfigurable manufacturing systems. In *2015 5th International Conference on the Internet of Things (IOT)*. IEEE, 2015.
- Oracle Corporation. *Java Platform, Standard Edition 8 Documentation*. Oracle, 2014. URL <https://docs.oracle.com/javase/8/docs/>.
- Inc. Pivotal Software. *Spring Boot Reference Documentation: Version 2.4.5*. VMware, 2021. URL <https://docs.spring.io/spring-boot/docs/2.4.5/reference/html/>.
- Springdoc Team. *Springdoc OpenAPI: Documentation for Version 1.5.2*, 2021a. URL <https://springdoc.org/>.
- Hibernate Team. *Hibernate ORM Documentation. Version 1.0.0*, 2001. URL <https://hibernate.org/orm/>.
- PostgreSQL Global Development Group. *PostgreSQL 11 Documentation*, 2018. URL <https://www.postgresql.org/docs/11/index.html>.
- RabbitMQ Team. *RabbitMQ Server: Version 3.8.16*, 2021b. URL <https://github.com/rabbitmq/rabbitmq-server/releases/tag/v3.8.16>.
- Inc. Docker. *Docker Engine Release Notes: Version 18.09.7*, 2019. URL <https://docs.docker.com/engine/release-notes/18.09>.
- Donald R. Jones. Optimization in the automotive industry. In *Optimization and Industry: New Frontiers*, pages 39–58. Springer US, Boston, MA, 2003.
- K. Giannakos, D. Tsakoumis, S. Plitsos, G. Koronakos, G. Vivo, and P. Eirinakis. Industrial application of the bipartite tsp in robotic pick-and-place operations. In *11th IFAC MIM 2025*, Trondheim, Norway, 2025.
- Aymen Gannouni et al. A blueprint description of production scheduling models using asset administration shells. *Production and Manufacturing Research*, 12(1):1–15, 2024. doi:10.1080/21693277.2024.2324339.